

ARCHEOLOGIA VENETA

JOURNAL OF ANCIENT STUDIES
ON NORTH-EASTERN ITALY

XLVIII-2025

Società Archeologica Veneta OdV

ARCHEOLOGIA VENETA

*JOURNAL OF ANCIENT STUDIES
ON NORTH-EASTERN ITALY*

XLVIII – 2025

SOCIETÀ ARCHEOLOGICA VENETA - ODV

Iniziativa editoriale promossa e realizzata da

con il contributo di

SAV OdV
cinque per mille 2025 (redditi 2024)

in collaborazione con

UNIVERSITÀ
DEGLI STUDI
DI PADOVA

Università
Ca'Foscari
Venezia
Dipartimento di
Studi Umanistici

UNIVERSITÀ
di **VERONA**
Dipartimento
di **CULTURE E CIVILTÀ**

MINISTERO
DELLA
CULTURA

Soprintendenza Archeologia,
Belle Arti e Paesaggio
per le province di
Verona, Rovigo e Vicenza

Soprintendenza Archeologia,
Belle Arti e Paesaggio
per le Province di Padova, Treviso e Belluno

Soprintendenza Archeologia,
Belle Arti e Paesaggio
per la città metropolitana di Venezia

Rivista inserita nel progetto ZENODO

ISSN 0392-9876

ARCHEOLOGIA VENETA

JOURNAL OF ANCIENT STUDIES ON NORTH-EASTERN ITALY

XLVIII – 2025

Rivista scientifica annuale double-blind peer reviewed

SOCIETÀ ARCHEOLOGICA VENETA - ODV - PADOVA

Comitato scientifico:

GIULIO CARRARO - direttore responsabile
MICHELE ASOLATI
PATRIZIA BASSO
CARLO BELTRAME
JACOPO BONETTO
BRUNELLA BRUNO
HEIMO DOLENZ
GIOVANNA GAMBACURTA
FULVIA MAINARDIS
ROBERT MATIJAŠIĆ
MARA GIOIA MIGLIAVACCA
ELISA POSSENTI
MARISA RIGONI
CECILIA ROSSI
CINZIA ROSSIGNOLI
DIRK STEUERNAGEL
FRANCESCA VERONESE
PAOLA ZANOVELLO
ARTURO ZARA

Comitato redazionale:

ARTURO ZARA - direttore editoriale
VALENTINA FAMARI - vicedirettore di redazione
CINZIA BETTINESCHI - segretario di redazione
GIOVANNI AZZALIN
VALENTINA BARATELLA
GIULIO CARRARO
ANDREA COZZA
MATTEO FUSARI
GIORGIO GARATTI
ANDREA GIUNTO
CHIARA MARCOLONGO
MICOL MASOTTI
MICHELE MATTEAZZI
VERONICA VENCO

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International - 2025

Società Archeologica Veneta OdV - Padova, via Timavo n. 13, 35135 Padova
tel. 349/3682650; c.f. 80009900285

pec: archeologicaveneta@pec.csvpadova.org

mail società: archeologicaveneta@gmail.com

mail redazione: redazione.archeologiaveneta@gmail.com

web: www.archeologicaveneta.com

Registro Operatori Comunicazione ROC n. 6675

Registri delle Organizzazioni di Volontariato:

Registro delle Associazioni del Comune di Padova, n. 699

Registro Unico Nazionale Terzo Settore (RUNTS), n. Rep. 53342

Autorizzazione del Tribunale di Padova n. 584 dell'8.2.1978

Annotazione del 3 agosto 2022 al n. 584 Registro Stampa

La rivista viene distribuita gratuitamente ai Soci ordinari della SAV in regola con la quota sociale

Progetto grafico e impaginazione: Arturo Zara

Per le annate XLV-2022, XLVI-2023, XLVII-2024, *Archeologia Veneta* si è avvalsa delle valutazioni dei seguenti *Referee*:

Alessandro Asta	Maria Cristina Guidotti
Leonardo Bernardi	Giovanni Leonardi
Alfredo Buonopane	Chiara Mattioli
Maria Stella Busana	Maria Grazia Melis
Bruno Callegher	Luisa Migliorati
Lorenzo Calvelli	Simonetta Minguzzi
Fabio Cavulli	Giulia Morpurgo
Giuliana Cavalieri Manasse	Elisabetta Roffia
Michele Cupitò	Maria Angela Ruta Serafini
Margherita Ferri	Paola Salzani
Andrea Gariboldi	Giuseppe Sassatelli
Sauro Gelichi	Peter Scherrer
Andrea Raffaele Ghiotto	Martino Serafini
Federica Gonzato	Jacopo Turchetto
Giovanni Gorini	Emanuele Vaccaro
Stefan Groh	Claudio Zaccaria

Il Comitato Scientifico ringrazia i gentili Colleghi per la disponibilità e per il fattivo contributo alla qualità della Rivista.

Nel triennio 2022-2024 sono stati presentati al Comitato Scientifico 48 abstract, sottoposti per la pubblicazione 39 contributi, di cui 4 non pubblicati a seguito di revisione.

Società Archeologica Veneta - OdV

Elenco dei soci

Anno associativo 2025

Vanessa Baratella

Claudio Barin

Lucia Barin

Cinzia Bettineschi

Elodia Bianchin Citton

Bonvicino Bonvicini

Loredana Capuis

Giulio Carraro

Gabriella Centanin

Anna Maria Chieco Bianchi

Stefania Cipollone

Andrea Cozza

Francesco Cozza

Filippo De Angeli

Anacleto Della Valle

Sara Emanuele

Valentina Famari

Tommaso Fantin

Elisabetta Favaron

Luciano Ferrario

Giovanna Gambacurta

Giorgio Garatti

Andrea Raffaele Ghiotto

Ivano Giacomini

Andrea Giunto

Marta Jorfida

Luigi Magnini

Chiara Marcolongo

Michele Matteazzi

Alessandra Menegazzi

Maria Cristina Mengotti

Michelangelo Munarini

Museo di Montebelluna

Silvia Paltinieri

Francesca Pandolfo

Sonia Pigato

Adolfo Piron

Camillo Riello Pera

Noemi Ruberti

Daniela Sacco

Giovanna Sandrini

Luca Sciola

Graziano Serra

Francesco Tavella

Loris Vedovato

Stefano Vicari

Daniele Zampierin

Paola Zanollo

Arturo Zara

Editoriale

Giulio Carraro

Arturo Zara

presidente SAV OdV e direttore responsabile

vicepresidente SAV OdV e direttore editoriale

Con il presente numero, *Archeologia Veneta* si colloca all'interno di uno dei nodi più delicati e attuali del dibattito archeologico italiano, quello relativo al rapporto tra tutela, ricerca e trasformazioni del territorio. Negli ultimi mesi, tali dinamiche si sono rese particolarmente evidenti nel Nord-Est, dove la densità della stratificazione storica, l'intensità delle opere infrastrutturali e la complessità dei processi decisionali offrono un ambito di osservazione privilegiato. Appare dunque sempre più urgente interrogarsi sul ruolo dell'archeologo e sul senso stesso della pratica archeologica in questi contesti. La sfida non consiste soltanto nel documentare correttamente ciò che emerge, ma nel restituire dignità scientifica e visibilità a ricerche che spesso nascono in condizioni complesse e frammentarie. In questo quadro, la capacità di trasformare gli interventi preventivi in progetti di ricerca coerenti e pubblicati rappresenta un obiettivo imprescindibile.

Non meno rilevante è il rapporto con le comunità e con il territorio. Le grandi opere incidono profondamente sulla percezione dei luoghi e generano, talvolta, conflitti e diffidenze. L'archeologia può svolgere un ruolo importante nel rendere comprensibile la profondità storica delle trasformazioni in atto, contribuendo a costruire una maggiore consapevolezza culturale. Ciò comporta tuttavia un ulteriore impegno sul piano comunicativo e nella restituzione dei risultati, preservando la complessità del dato scientifico ed evitando semplificazioni riduttive.

L'archeologia del Nord-Est dispone di strumenti, competenze e tradizioni di studio che le consentono di proporsi come laboratorio di buone pratiche. La lunga attenzione rivolta ai temi del paesaggio, della lunga durata e dell'integrazione tra fonti diverse costituisce una base solida su cui costruire modelli virtuosi, capaci di coniugare tutela, ricerca e sviluppo.

Questo volume di *Archeologia Veneta* si colloca dunque in un dibattito aperto e necessario. Difendere il rigore scientifico, valorizzare la ricerca prodotta nei cantieri, restituire voce ai contesti del Nord-Est significa riaffermare che l'archeologia non è un costo da gestire, ma una forma di conoscenza indispensabile per comprendere e abitare consapevolmente il territorio contemporaneo.

Alla luce di questi presupposti, anche quest'anno i contributi della nostra Rivista abbracciano un ampio arco cronologico, dall'età protostorica alla tarda antichità, e una vasta area dell'Italia nord-orientale, spingendosi peraltro ad includere un intervento relativo a un rinvenimento numismatico istriano, ai margini della *Regio X* augustea. Le ricerche proposte hanno inoltre carattere multidisciplinare, interdisciplinare e transdisciplinare, spaziando – grazie anche all'ausilio delle scienze applicate – dalle analisi cronologiche e tipologiche, a quelle territoriali ed epigrafiche, sino a toccare i sempre più preminenti temi della conservazione e della valorizzazione.

Con soddisfazione, inoltre, accogliamo due articoli in inglese: l'utilizzo della lingua straniera veicolare, che la Rivista cercherà in futuro di incentivare ulteriormente tra gli autori, dà ai contributi e, in termini più ampi, ad *Archeologia Veneta* un maggiore potenziale informativo, che, prendendo le mosse da un territorio ben definito, quello dell'Italia nord-orientale, si proietta verso una dimensione più ampia e di carattere internazionale.

INDICE
XLVIII – 2025

BELLUNO

Un complesso monetale di età romana da Castellavazzo (Longarone, Belluno) 2

Jacopo Marcer

Necropoli di Piasentòt-San Donato di Lamon (BL). Monete dagli scavi del 2018 18

Bruno Callegher

PADOVA

Le tombe della Nuova Casa di Ricovero di Este. Un contributo alla definizione della ritualità funeraria nel comparto euganeo tra il Bronzo finale e gli inizi dell'età del Ferro alla luce dei dati archeologici, antropologici e paleobotanici 40

Elodia Bianchin Citton (a cura di), Elisabetta Castiglioni, Leonardo Lamanna, Anny Mattucci, Mauro Rottoli

La situla Randi 34 di Este e il suo coperchio: tecnologia, note di restauro e nuova proposta di restituzione grafica 86

Stefano Buson

Ateste: la "via sacra" 104

Cinzia Tagliaferro

ROVIGO

Le risorse ambientali nell'insediamento romano di San Basilio: note preliminari dallo studio dei macroresti vegetali 114

Noemi Ruberti, Marco Marchesini, Caterina Previato

Atestine and Aquileian models in funerary sculpture from Polesine 130

Luca Scalco

TREVISO

Oderzo (TV): un intervento di manutenzione straordinaria nell'area archeologica del foro e della basilica a oltre trent'anni dal progetto di restauro e valorizzazione 142

Sara Emanuele, Paola Crucianelli

Fossalta di Portogruaro (Venice), Borgo Valle. Moulded Gaulish terra sigillata.

New evidence on terra sigillata from the *ager* of *Iulia Concordia*

Francesca Pandolfo*

Riassunto

In oltre quarant'anni di attività sul campo dispiegate capillarmente in tutto in territorio concordiese, il Gruppo Archeologico del Veneto Orientale ha raccolto una cospicua mole di reperti archeologici, prevalentemente riferibili a età romana, che sono per lo più rimasti inediti e dei quali si è recentemente avviato lo studio. Con il presente contributo si intende esporre quanto emerso dall'analisi dei frammenti di terra sigillata, per fornire nuovi dati utili alla conoscenza di questa variegata classe per quanto riguarda le forme, le produzioni e la distribuzione nel territorio.

Parole Chiave

Terra sigillata, *Iulia Concordia*, archeologia del territorio, rinvenimenti di superficie

Abstract

In over forty years of extensive fieldwork throughout the *Iulia Concordia* countryside, the Archaeological Group of Eastern Veneto has collected a considerable amount of archaeological finds, mainly dating back to the Roman period, which have mostly remained unpublished and have recently been studied. The present contribution intends to present what has emerged from the analysis of the terra sigillata, in order to provide new useful data for our knowledge of this varied class in terms of the forms and productions attested, as well as their diffusion in rural settlements.

Keywords

Terra sigillata, *Iulia Concordia*, landscape archaeology, surface findings

1. Introduction

Established in 1982, the Archaeological Group of Eastern Veneto (Gr.A.V.O.) has made significant contributions to our understanding of settlement patterns in the territory formerly belonging to the Roman colony of *Iulia Concordia*. Through extensive surface surveys, they have identified over 170 sites, predominantly dating to the Roman period. The group's comprehensive work culminated in the publication of two archaeological maps in 1985 and 2002¹, with numerous subsequent reports and findings.

As part of an ongoing research project centered on the maritime villa of Mutteron dei Frati in Bibione (San Michele al Tagliamento, VE), which also aims to investigate the coastal area of the *ager Concordiensis* during the Roman period², it became natural to broaden the scope of research. This expansion particularly involved initiating a systematic study of the finds collected by Gr.A.V.O. members, which had received limited attention in the aforementioned publications.

The examination of terra sigillata, notable for its high number of diagnostic fragments,

* Università degli Studi di Padova, Dipartimento dei Beni Culturali
francesca.pandolfo@unipd.it

offers a valuable opportunity to enrich our understanding of these artifacts in *Venetia* and to formulate preliminary socio-economic considerations about the settlements in the Concordia territory. While the terra sigillata found in the urban center of Concordia has been well-documented³, there are few stratigraphically documented contexts from the *ager*, and limited data on pottery findings, specifically terra sigillata⁴. The objective of this investigation, therefore, is to provide new data to help fill this documentary gap.

However, surface finds inherently present limitations, lacking any stratigraphic association. This study is further constrained by the partiality of available materials, originating

from only a portion of the identified Roman-age contexts or more recently discovered sites. Additionally, there is a qualitative and quantitative disparity of finds for each site, almost certainly due to selective collection methods rather than solely the actual presence of surface material. Furthermore, the high fragmentation rate and generally poor state of preservation often complicate the identification of forms and types.

2. The contexts of discovery

The terra sigillata fragments in this study originate from 30 contexts (*tab. 1, fig. 1*)⁵, known almost exclusively through surface

fig. 1. Distribution of terra sigillata productions in the *ager* of Iulia Concordia (elaboration by A. Vacilotto).

MAPPA 2002	ID	SITE	TYPOLOGY	CHRONOLOGY	NORTH ITALIAN SIGILLATA	ITALIAN SIGILLATA	GAULISH SIGILLATA	EASTERN SIGILLATA	AFRICAN RED SLIP
---	54M	Annone Veneto, via Villalata			X		X		
83	52M	Portogruaro, Pradipozzo (Fornace)	Farm	1st-2nd c. AD	X				
93	51M	Portogruaro, Summaga	Farm	1st c. BC - 2nd c. AD	X	X			
29	53M	Cinto Caomaggiore, San Biagio	Villa	1st-3rd c. AD	X	X			
45	42M	Teglio Veneto, Pais	Farm	1st-3rd c. AD	X				
44	43M	Teglio Veneto, Pais	Villa	1st-3rd c. AD	X	X			
48	38M	Fossalta di Portogruaro, Gorgo (Cesioi dei Laghi)	Villa	1st-3rd c. AD (?)		X			
52	36M	Fossalta di Portogruaro, Gorgo	Farm	1st-2nd c. AD	X				
54	41M	Fossalta di Portogruaro, Perarut	Farm	1st-2nd c. AD	X	X			
55	34M	Fossalta di Portogruaro, Roiatte Valladis	Villa with necropolis	1st c. BC - 4th c. AD	X	X	X		X
---	33M	Fossalta di Portogruaro, Barbuio	Necropolis		X				
65	29M	Portogruaro, Vado (Fratrine)	Farm	1st-2nd c. AD (?)	X				
66	9M	Fossalta di Portogruaro, Vado	Farm (?)	1st-2nd c. AD (?)	X	X	X		X
69	8M	Fossalta di Portogruaro, Villanova (Boscato)	Villa	1st-3rd c. AD (?)	X				
76	1M	San Stino di Livenza, Biverone	Villa	1st-2nd c. AD	X				
77	2M	San Stino di Livenza, Biverone	Farm	1st-3rd c. AD	X			X	
106	35M	Fossalta di Portogruaro, Case Vianello	Farm	1st-3rd c. AD (?)	X				
110	4M	Portogruaro, San Giacomo	Necropolis	1st-3rd c. AD	X				
117	13M	Portogruaro, Palazzo Valle	Farm	1st-2nd c. AD (?)	X				
119	49M	Portogruaro, Giussago	Necropolis	1st-2nd c. AD	X				
---	17M	Portogruaro, Borgo Rivago				X			
126	50M	Portogruaro, Centa	Villa	1st-3rd c. AD		X			
---	18M	Portogruaro, Centa Taglio			X				
128	14M	Portogruaro, Borgo Valle	Villa	1st-3rd c. AD (?)	X	X	X		X
127	15M	Portogruaro, Vescovado	Villa	1st-2nd c. AD (?)	X	X			X
131	16M	Portogruaro, Bonifica Viola	Farm with necropolis	1st-2nd c. AD (?)	X				
139	22M	Portogruaro, Marina di Lugugnana	Villa	1st-2nd c. AD			X		
---	25M	Caorle, Marango			X				
157	26M	Caorle, Brussa (Ate)	Villa	1st-5th c. AD	X	X		X	X
---	27M	Caorle, Vallevecchia			X			X	

tab. 1. The contexts of discovery.

surveys⁶. These sites are distributed across the low and middle plain area of Eastern Veneto, between the Livenza and Tagliamento rivers, an area that in antiquity belonged to the *ager* of the colony of *Iulia Concordia*.

Due to the survey methodology that led to the identification of these sites, functional interpretation has been based solely on the categories of materials and the areal dimensions of the scatters. Excluding the six sites reported after the publication of Gr.A.V.O.'s second archaeological map⁷, the remaining have been interpreted as isolated rural settlements. These include both medium and large *villae* (11 sites) and more modest farms (11 sites)⁸, in a couple of cases associated with predial necropolises. Only two contexts have been hypothesized as necropolises distinct from habitations.

The majority of sites are concentrated in the southeastern area of the *ager*, where the presence of the elevated and dry ridge of the major branch of the *Tiliaventum* makes it highly attractive for settlement. Of the 30 sites considered, 16 are located between the area where the *Via Annia* crosses the river, near Vado (Fossalta di Portogruaro), and the river mouth, near present-day Brussa (Caorle). Moreover, the distribution of the sites highlights the importance of road networks in settlement choices, primarily the *Via Annia*, but also the *Postumia* and the secondary road that, branching off from the *Annia* at Vado, crossed the area currently known as Pars and connected to the *Aquileia-Virunum* road.

The contexts have generally yielded an extremely low number of fragments, rarely exceeding ten pieces. A few notable sites

deviate from this pattern, providing about twenty fragments each (sites 66=09M, 128=14M, 157=26M). The site of Roiatte Valladis (site 55=34M) has yielded over 40 small fragments, but given the extreme fragmentation of these elements, it is likely that they represent a much smaller number of original objects.

3. Terra sigillata from the Concordia territory sites

The analysis of terra sigillata from the Concordia territory encompassed 172 fragments, of which only 80 were diagnostic, revealing a considerable morphological variety (*tab. 2*). Among the identified productions, North Italian wares significantly predominate, although imported vessels from Central Italy, South and Central Gaul, Asia Minor, and Africa are also present (*fig. 2*)⁹. Notably, eight stamped fragments were identified, some fragmentary and only one illegible (*tab. 3, fig. 3*).

3.1. Italian productions

Among the terra sigillata produced in the Italian Peninsula, Padana sigillata is the best-documented, with 115 fragments (44 diagnostic), while only 31 fragments are attributable to Central Italian workshops (21 diagnostic). The vast majority of North Italian sigillata fragments appear to belong to plain ware (102 fragments), with 13 pieces attributable to mould-decorated forms. The Central Italian products, however, are exclusively represented by plain specimens.

Morphological analysis of the plain Padana sigillata assemblage has identified 12

SITE	SITE ID	PRODUCTION	FORM	TYPE	N° FRAGS	DECORATION	IMAGE
Fossalta di Portogruaro, Vado	66=09M	North Italian	Plate	Consp. 18.2 (?)	1		pl. 1.2
Portogruaro, Palazzo Valle	117=13M	North Italian	Plate	Consp. 18.2	1		pl. 1.1
Portogruaro, Borgo Valle	128=14M	North Italian	Plate	Consp. 18.2	1		pl. 1.3
Fossalta di Portogruaro, Vado	66=09M	North Italian	Plate	Consp. 18.2	1		pl. 1.4
Portogruaro, Frattine	65=29M	North Italian	Plate	Consp. 18.2	1		pl. 1.5
Teglio V.to, Pars	45=42M	North Italian	Plate	Consp. 4.6	1	Spiral	pl. 1.6
San Stino di Livenza, Biverone	76=01M	North Italian	Plate	Consp. 20.4	1	Garland and vine leaf	pl. 1.7
Fossalta di Portogruaro, Gorgo	52=36M	North Italian	Plate	Consp. 21.3	1		pl. 1.8
Fossalta di Portogruaro, Roiatte Valladis	55=34M	North Italian	Plate	Consp. 20.4 / 21.3 / 21.7	1		pl. 2.1
Fossalta di Portogruaro, Roiatte Valladis	55=34M	North Italian	Plate	Consp. 3.3	1		pl. 2.2
Fossalta di Portogruaro, Gorgo	52=36M	North Italian	Plate	Consp. 3	1		pl. 2.3
Portogruaro, Palazzo Valle	117=13M	North Italian	Plate		1		
Portogruaro, Pradipozzo	83=52M	North Italian	Bowl (?)	Consp. 7.1 (?)	1		
Caorle, Brussa (Are)	157=26M	North Italian	Bowl	Consp. 26.1	1		pl. 2.4
Fossalta di Portogruaro, Roiatte Valladis	55=34M	North Italian	Bowl	Consp. 29	1		pl. 2.5
Fossalta di Portogruaro, Roiatte Valladis	55=34M	North Italian	Bowl	Consp. 36.4	1		pl. 2.7
Fossalta di Portogruaro, Vado	66=09M	North Italian	Bowl	Consp. 37.3	1		pl. 2.6
Portogruaro, Borgo Valle	128=14M	North Italian	Bowl	Consp. B 3.12	1		pl. 2.9
Fossalta di Portogruaro, Roiatte Valladis	55=34M	North Italian	Bowl	Consp. B 3 / 4 (?)	1		pl. 2.10
San Stino di Livenza, Biverone	77=02M	North Italian	Bowl (?)		1		
Portogruaro, Lugugnana (Bonifica Viola)	131=16M	North Italian	Bowl (?)		1		
Fossalta di Portogruaro, Vado	66=09M	Tardo Padana	Bowl	Consp. 43	1		pl. 2.11
Teglio V.to, Pars	44=43M	North Italian	Jug		1		
Annone Veneto, via Villalta	54M	North Italian			3		
Portogruaro, Summaga	93=51M	North Italian			6		
Fossalta di Portogruaro, Case Vianello	106=35M	North Italian or Tardo Padana (?)			2		
Fossalta di Portogruaro, Roiatte Valladis	55=34M	North Italian and Tardo Padana			29		
Fossalta di Portogruaro, Perarut	54=41M	North Italian			1		

tab. 2. Terra sigillata from the Concordia territory sites.

SITE	SITE ID	PRODUCTION	FORM	TYPE	N° FRAGS	DECORATION	IMAGE
Portogruaro, Frattine	65=29M	North Italian			8		
Fossalta di Portogruaro, Vado	66=09M	North Italian			7		
Portogruaro, San Giacomo (terreno Anese)	110=94M	North Italian			1		
Fossalta di Portogruaro, Villanova (Boscato)	69=08M	North Italian and Tardo Padana			4		
Portogruaro, Giussago	119=49M	North Italian			1		
Portogruaro, Centa Taglio	18M	North Italian			1		
Portogruaro, Borgo Valle	128=14M	North Italian			3		
Portogruaro, Lugugnana (Bonifica Viola)	131=16M	North Italian			1		
Caorle, Brussa (Are)	157=26M	North Italian			2		
Portogruaro, Borgo Valle	128=14M	Mid-imperial Padana	Bowl	Jorio 10 / Stuani - Mantovani 7	1		pl. 3.1
Fossalta di Portogruaro, Roiatte Valladis	55=34M	Mid-imperial Padana	Bowl	Stuani - Mantovani 11	1		pl. 3.2
Fossalta di Portogruaro, Roiatte Valladis	55=34M	Mid-imperial Padana	Bowl	Stuani - Mantovani 11	1		
Portogruaro, Palazzo Valle	117=13M	Mid-imperial Padana	Bowl	Stuani - Mantovani 11	1		pl. 3.5
Portogruaro, Borgo Valle	128=14M	Mid-imperial Padana	Bowl	Stuani - Mantovani 11	1		pl. 3.3
Caorle, Brussa (Are)	157=26M	Mid-imperial Padana	Bowl	Stuani - Mantovani 11	2		pl. 3.4
Portogruaro, Summaga	93=51M	Mid-imperial Padana	Bowl	Stuani - Mantovani 10 / 11	1		pl. 3.6
Portogruaro, Borgo Valle	128=14M	North Italian	Crater	Mazzeo Saracino 11D = Mantovani 9	1		pl. 4.1
Fossalta di Portogruaro, Perarut	54=41M	North Italian	Bowl	Consp. R 13	1	Ovoli, poorly preserved	pl. 4.4
Fossalta di Portogruaro, Roiatte Valladis	55=34M	North Italian	Bowl	Consp. R 13	1		pl. 4.2
Fossalta di Portogruaro, Roiatte Valladis	55=34M	North Italian	Bowl	Consp. R 13	1	Two heart-shaped leafs, poorly preserved	
Fossalta di Portogruaro, Roiatte Valladis	55=34M	North Italian	Bowl (?)	Consp. R 13 (?)	1		pl. 4.8
Fossalta di Portogruaro, Barbuio	33M	North Italian	Bowl	Consp. R 13	1	Palmette	pl. 4.6
Fossalta di Portogruaro, Barbuio	33M	North Italian	Bowl	Consp. R 13	1		pl. 4.11
Portogruaro, Frattine	65=29M	North Italian	Bowl	Consp. R 13	1		pl. 4.10

SITE	SITE ID	PRODUCTION	FORM	TYPE	N° FRAGS	DECORATION	IMAGE
Fossalta di Portogruaro, Vado	66=09M	North Italian	Bowl	Consp. R 13	1	Palmette and heart-shaped leaf	pl. 4.5
Portogruaro, Giussago	119=49M	North Italian	Bowl	Consp. R 13	1		pl. 4.9
Portogruaro, Borgo Valle	128=14M	North Italian	Bowl	Consp. R 13	1	Bird	pl. 4,7; fig. 3
Caorle, Marango	25M	North Italian	Bowl	Consp. R 13	1	Rosette frieze	pl. 4.3
Fossalta di Portogruaro, Perarut	54=41M	North Italian	Bowl (?)		1	Alternating overlapping ovoli	
Fossalta di Portogruaro, Vado	66=09M	Italian	Plate	Consp. 12.2	1		pl. 5.1
Portogruaro, Borgo Valle	128=14M	Italian	Plate	Consp. 18.2 (?)	1	Masque	pl. 5.2
Portogruaro, Vescodavo	127=15M	Italian	Plate	Consp. 18.2	1		pl. 5.3
Fossalta di Portogruaro, Gorgo (Cesiol dei Laghi)	48=38M	Italian	Plate	Consp. 18.3	1		pl. 5.4
Caorle, Brussa (Are)	157=26M	Italian	Plate	Consp. 20.3 / 21.2	1		pl. 5.5
Caorle, Brussa (Are)	157=26M	Italian	Plate	Consp. 19.3 / 21.7	1		pl. 5.6
Caorle, Brussa (Are)	157=26M	Italian	Plate	Consp. 20.4	1	Spiral	pl. 5.7
Portogruaro, Borgo Valle	128=14M	Italian	Plate	Consp. 20.4	1	Garland (<i>Noricum</i> G1 ?)	pl. 5.8
Cinto Caomaggiore	29=53M	Italian	Plate	Consp. 20.4 / 21.7	2	Garland; Palmette (<i>Noricum</i> O12)	pl. 6.1
Cinto Caomaggiore	29=53M	Italian	Plate	Consp. 20.4 / 21.7	2	Vine leaf (<i>Noricum</i> V9)	pl. 6.2
Cinto Caomaggiore	29=53M	Italian	Plate	Consp. 20.4 / 21.7	1	Garland (<i>Noricum</i> G23); Palmette	pl. 6.3
Portogruaro, Borgo Valle	128=14M	Italian	Plate	Consp. B 1.5	1	Rouletting	pl. 6.4
Fossalta di Portogruaro, Vado	66=09M	Italian	Plate		1	Rouletting	
Portogruaro, Borgo Rivago	17M	Italian	Bowl	Consp. 26.1-2	1	Spiral (<i>Noricum</i> S9)	pl. 6.5
Portogruaro, Centa	126=50M	Italian	Bowl	Consp. 9	1	Rouletting	pl. 6.6
Fossalta di Portogruaro, Vado	66=09M	Italian	Bowl	Consp. B 3.16	1		pl. 6.7
Portogruaro, Summaga	93=51M	Italian	Bowl	Consp. B3.14	1		pl. 6.8
Fossalta di Portogruaro, Perarut	54=41M	Italian	Bowl		1	Spiral	
Portogruaro, Summaga	29=53M	Italian			4		
Fossalta di Portogruaro, Roiatte Valladis	55=34M	Italian			2		
Fossalta di Portogruaro, Vado	66=09M	Italian			1		
Teglio V.to, Pars	45=42M	South Gaulish	Bowl	Drag. 37	1		pl. 7.2

SITE	SITE ID	PRODUCTION	FORM	TYPE	N° FRAGS	DECORATION	IMAGE
Fossalta di Portogruaro, Vado	66=09M	South Gaulish	Bowl	Drag. 37	1	Ovolo and bead frieze	pl. 7.3
Portogruaro, Borgo Valle	128=14M	South Gaulish	Bowl	Drag. 37	1	Ovolo and bead frieze; bear (Osw.1611); shrub (H.329)	pl. 7.1
Portogruaro, Marina di Luggnana	139=22M	South Gaulish	Bowl	Drag. 37	1	Shrub (H.329) (?)	pl. 7.5
Caorle, Brussa (Are)	157=26M	South Gaulish	Bowl (?)		1	Garland	pl. 7.4
Fossalta di Portogruaro, Roiatte Valladis	55=34M	South Gaulish	Bowl (?)		1	Illegibile	
Annone Veneto, via Villalta	54M	South Gaulish	Bowl (?)		1		
Portogruaro, Borgo Valle	128=14M	South Gaulish	Bowls		3		fig. 4
Portogruaro, Borgo Valle	128=14M	Central Gaulish	Bowl	Drag. 37	1	Ovolo and bead frieze (?)	pl. 7.6
Caorle, Brussa (Are)	157=26M	Oriente B2	Plate	Hayes 60	1		pl. 8.1
Caorle, Brussa (Are)	157=26M	LRC (?)	Dish (?)		1		pl. 8.3
San Stino di Livenza, Biverone	77=02M	ARS A2	Plate	Hayes 27	1		pl. 8.4
Portogruaro, Vescodavo	127=15M	ARS D1	Dish	Hayes 58A	1		pl. 8.5
Portogruaro, Borgo Valle	128=14M	ARS D1	Dish	Hayes 59B	1		pl. 8.6
Fossalta di Portogruaro, Vado	66=09M	ARS D	Dish	Hayes 50B	1		pl. 8.7
Fossalta di Portogruaro, Roiatte Valladis	55=34M	ARS D			1	Impressed geometrical decoration, poorly preserved. Hayes Style A(ii)-(iii)	pl. 8.8
Fossalta di Portogruaro, Roiatte Valladis	55=34M	ARS D			1		
Fossalta di Portogruaro, Vado	66=09M	ARS D			1	Impressed geometrical decoration. Hayes Style A(ii)-(iii)	pl. 8.9
Caorle, Brussa (Are)	157=26M	ARS D			2		
Caorle, Brussa (Are)	157=26M	ARS			2		

SITE	ID SITE	POTTER	STAMP	CARTOUCHE	OCK	PRODUCTION	FORM	TYPE	CRONOLOGY	IMAGE
Portogruaro, Vescovado	127=15M	Dento	DENTO	rectangular	731.1	Po Valley	Bowl	Consp. B 4.13	10 BC - 10 AD	pl. 2.10; 9.1
Caorle, Valleviecchia	27M	Mae Pates	MAE/PATIS	rectangular	1083.2	Bologna?	Bowl (?)	Consp. 38 (?)	late 1st c. BC - early 1st c. AD	pl. 9.2
Fossalta di Portogruaro, Roiatte Valladis	55=34M	Gellius	GELL	planta pedis	878.31-37	Arezzo	Bowl		10-50 AD	pls. 6.9; 9.3
Portogruaro, Borgo Valle	128=14M	Gellius	GE[---]	planta pedis	878	Arezzo			10-50 AD	pl. 9.4
Teglio Veneto, Pars	45=42M	M. Perennius Crescens	M^P^ECRES	planta pedis	1408.12	Arezzo			30-60 AD	pl. 9.5
Portogruaro, Borgo Valle	128=14M	M. Perennius Crescens	M^P[---]	planta pedis	1408	Arezzo			30-60 AD	pl. 9.6
Caorle, Valleviecchia	27M			planta pedis		ESB (?)				pls. 8.2; 9.7
Caorle, Brussa (Are)	157=26M			planta pedis		ESB (?)				pl. 9.8

tab. 3. Potter's stamps on terra sigillata.

fig. 2. Productions and forms of terra sigillata in the *ager of Iulia Concordia*.

plates, 11 cups and 1 jug or table amphora, the latter evidenced by a small circular-section handle fragment. Among the plates, 11 fragments were typologically classifiable, while one specimen could only be generically identified. The majority are plates with vertical concave-convex rims of the *Consp.* 18.2 type (5 specimens, *pl.* 1.1-5), dating to the early 1st century AD¹⁰. A fragment identified as *Consp.* 4.6 (*pl.* 1.6), characterized by a rim indistinct from its convex wall and decorated with an applied spiral, is attributable to the Tiberian-Claudian period. Three plates with vertical band rims, corresponding to types *Consp.* 20 and 21 (*p.l.s.* 1.7-8, 2.1), date to the mid-1st century AD. These include a clearly identifiable *Consp.* 20.4 rim, datable to the Claudian period or later based on its applied decoration, and a wall fragment belonging to the *Consp.*

21.3 variant. The classification of the third rim fragment remains uncertain due to its poor preservation state. Two *Consp.* 3 plates (*pl.* 2.2-3), featuring flared walls and rounded everted rims, likely date to the latter half of the century.

The assemblage of cups attributed to the early imperial plain Padana production is comparable in number to that of the plates, with the diagnostic elements revealing a diverse typological repertoire. A fragment, possibly belonging to a *Consp.* 7.1 cup with flared walls, dates to the Augustan period. Forms produced during the first half of the 1st century AD include the *Consp.* 26.1 truncated conical cup (*pl.* 2.4), the *Consp.* 29 cylindrical small cup with a slightly protruding foot (*pl.* 2.5), and the *Consp.* 36.4 and 37.3 hemispherical cups (*pl.* 2.6-7). Additionally, three bases with ring feet were identified.

fig. 3. Potter's stamps.

The poor preservation of one fragment precludes identification beyond its basic form (pl. 2.10). Another specimen, featuring the attachment of a rounded wall, likely dates to the 1st century AD, probably its first half (pl. 2.9). The third element exhibits a wall with an oblique profile (fig. 3.1; pl. 2.10). This last fragment bears the mark of the potter *Dento* impressed on the inner surface, in a rectangular cartouche (OCK 731.1), whose activity dates between 10 BC and 10 AD. Another base, lacking its foot, bears the signature MAE/PATIS inside a quadrangular cartouche (OCK 1083.2), dated between the Augustan age and the very early Tiberian period (fig. 3.2)¹¹. These two stamps represent significant new findings, as they are not documented in the urban center of *Iulia Concordia*, nor found among the published attestations from the Concordia area¹².

A single fragment of a curved rim, belonging to a hemispherical cup of type *Consp.* 43, is attributable to the so-called Tardo Padana production. This form can be chronologically placed between the mid-1st century and the mid-2nd century AD (pl. 2.11).

The assemblage of mid-imperial Padana products (2nd-3rd centuries AD) is characterized by a modest presence of specimens. In addition to a hemispherical cup identifiable as form *Jorio 10 / Stuani - Mantovani 7* (pl. 3.1)¹³, there are five other hemispherical ribbed cups corresponding to forms *Stuani - Mantovani 10* and *11* (pl. 3.2-6)¹⁴.

Within the mould-decorated Padana production, cups with high convex rim *Consp.* R13 are almost exclusively present. Twelve fragments are attributable to this form, of which 6 pertain to bowl portions (pl. 4.2-11). Their small size makes it difficult

to place them more precisely within known type variants and, consequently, to provide a more accurate chronological definition¹⁵. Therefore, the cups analyzed here can only be broadly dated to within the final decades of the 1st century BC. Among the decorative motifs, vegetable elements predominate, consisting of rosettes and heart-shaped leaves; only in one case was the depiction of a bird with a long beak, facing left, vaguely reminiscent of a pelican or ibis (fig. 4). The figure exhibits similarities to decorative motifs found on two cups: one from Faenza bearing the signature SIPA¹⁶, and another from *Lulia Concordia* attributed to the potter *Trypho*¹⁷. A comparable bird stamp, though facing right, is also observed on a cup from *Adria*¹⁸. However, the suboptimal preservation state of our specimen precludes a definitive stylistic attribution, rendering such comparisons tentative.

Due to morphological affinity, a fragment of an everted rim with triangular section and high convex neck has also been included in the group of mould-decorated North Italian sigillata (pl. 4.1). This is compatible with those of the cantharoid cup or, more likely, the crater described by L. Mazzeo Saracino in the second volume of the *Atlante* (forms 10D and 11D), both referable to the Augustan age¹⁹. The absence of decorated portions unfortunately precludes any consideration regarding attribution on a stylistic basis, although it should be emphasized that the vast majority of known findings are the work of artisans from the *Sarius* workshop.

Regarding the diagnostic fragments of Central Italian imports, all pertaining to plain

fig. 4. Fossalta di Portogruaro (Venice), Borgo Valle. Moulded North Italian terra sigillata.

production, 13 plates and 8 cups were identified. Among the plates, the oldest fragment belongs to a large base with a concentric band of roulette-impressed notches, of type *Consp. B 1.5* (pl. 6.4), chronologically placed in the early and middle Augustan age. A fragment of plate *Consp. 12.2*, with a slightly pronounced pendant rim, flattened slightly convex outer edge, and flared convex wall, is referable to the period between the end of the 1st century BC and the beginning of the following century (pl. 5.1). Coeval or slightly later is a fragment of plate *Consp. 19.3* or *21.7*, pertaining to the step placed approximately in the middle portion of the bowl, decorated with rouletting (pl. 5.6). Four fragments of plates with vertical rim, framed as types *Consp. 18.2*, *18.3*, and *20.3* or *21.2* (pl. 5.2-5), are attributable to the initial decades of the

1st century AD. With the exception of a fragment with an applied mask, for which no precise comparisons have been found, the other elements are apparently devoid of decoration, save for some thin incised lines on both the internal and external surfaces. Five plates of type *Consp.* 20.4 (or possibly *Consp.* 21.7), on which part of the applied decoration is preserved (*pis.* 5.7-8; 6.1-3), date to the middle of the century, perhaps even to the Neronian-Flavian age.

Regarding the cups, a base of type *Consp.* 9, referable to the middle-late Augustan age, with a low ring foot and slightly concave flared wall, on which a small portion of the roulette decoration is preserved above a double moulding (*pl.* 6.6), and the rim of *Consp.* 26.1 or 26.2, datable to the first half of the 1st century AD, which partially preserves the applied spiral (*pl.* 6.5), can be distinguished with a good degree of reliability. There are also two bases, identifiable as *Consp. B* 3.14 and 3.16 (*pl.* 6.7-8), associated with types that cover a good part of the production arc of Italian Sigillata, between the end of the 1st century BC and the middle of the 2nd century AD. Four cup bases of unidentified type bear the *in planta pedis* signatures of the potters impressed on the inner surface: in two cases, the stamps refer to the potter *Gellius*, active in Arezzo between 10 and 50 AD (OCK 878) (*fig.* 3.3-4)²⁰; coeval or slightly later, equally from the Arezzo production area, are two other marks of *M. Perennius Crescens*, whose activity is placed between 30 and 60 AD (OCK 1408) (*fig.* 3.5-6)²¹. The signatures of these two potters are also found in Concordia, with 5 and 1 attestations respectively²².

3.2. Gaulish productions

Among the surveyed fragments, there are 11 specimens of Gaulish import, almost all referable to South Gaulish manufactures (*pl.* 7.1-5), except for a single element of Central Gaulish production (*pl.* 7.6). Morphologically, excluding one fragment too small to determine form and possible decorations, all elements are attributable to cups with mould-made relief decoration, identifiable as type *Drag.* 37 when significant portions are present.

Among the South Gaulish specimens, a fragment of a *Drag.* 37 cup from Borgo Valle (site 128=14M), is noteworthy (*frontispiece*). It features a flabellate hunting scene in which a bear advancing to the left among vegetal scrolls can be recognized²³. The depiction of the animal, along with the stylistic rendering of the ovolo frieze that closes the scene at the top, seems to refer to the manufacture of *L. Cosius*, active in La Graufesenque between the end of the 1st century AD and the first decades of the following century²⁴. Elsewhere, the high fragmentation and poor state of preservation prevent a more precise stylistic analysis; the ornamental elements seem to be mostly attributable to vegetal fillers, and only in one case is it possible to recognize the silhouette of a quadruped, perhaps to be identified as an ungulate (*fig.* 5).

Imports from Central Gaul are limited to one specimen of a *Drag.* 37 cup, referable to the Lezoux workshop based on the characteristics of the fabric and surface treatment. The fragment preserves a small portion of the ovolo and bead row frieze that must have delimited the mould-decorated field at the top; however, the extremely fragmentary pres-

fig. 5. Fossalta di Portogruaro (Venice), Borgo Valle. Moulded Gaulish terra sigillata.

ervation does not allow for a more precise identification. The chronology is therefore to be understood generically between the 2nd and the first half of the 3rd century AD.

3.3. Eastern Mediterranean productions and dubious provenance

Imports of terra sigillata from the Eastern Mediterranean are documented with certainty only by one fragment of Eastern Sigillata B, whose workshops are to be located in the hinterland of Ephesus and which is the most exported production in the Adriatic among Eastern sigillata²⁵. It is a plate of type Hayes 60 (pl. 8.1), of which a portion of the wall with the characteristic moulding between the flared wall and the inturned rim is preserved; considering the technical and dimensional characteristics, the vessel can be attributed to an advanced phase of production (B2), indica-

tively datable between the last quarter of the 1st century AD and the middle of the 2nd.

Two bases referable to small open forms, which present maker's marks impressed on the inner surface, are difficult to frame, despite the technical characteristics of the texture and surface treatment seeming compatible with those of ESB production upon macroscopic analysis. The first fragment (fig. 3.7; pl. 8.2), with a low oblique foot, comparable to that of the truncated conical cups Hayes 68 and 70, bears a stamp *in planta pedis* with well-defined features, but difficult to interpret and therefore meriting further in-depth studies²⁶. The second base, lacking the foot, also bears a stamp *in planta pedis*, which is however illegible (fig. 3.8).

Doubts persist, finally, on another element of possible Eastern origin (pl. 8.3), which the characteristics of the ceramic

body and coating make similar to Phocaean Red Slip Ware (Late Roman C Ware)²⁷, produced in the Phocaea area and widely exported throughout the Mediterranean in late antiquity²⁸. From a morphological point of view, it is a bowl with a small ledge, which however seems only vaguely comparable to the *Hayes 3* form²⁹.

3.4. African productions

The assemblage of African Red Slip Ware consists of 11 fragments, pertaining to fabrics A (1 specimen) and especially D (8 specimens), both referable to the production sector of northern Tunisia. For 2 fragments, the poor state of preservation does not allow for a certain attribution to one of the productions. The diagnostic fragments are referable only to open forms such as plates and dishes: to the earliest production found (A2) belongs a flat base with a low, slightly oblique ring foot (*pl. 8.4*), like that found in type *Hayes 27*, dated between the second half of the 2nd and the beginning of the 3rd century AD. Dishes with flanged rim *Hayes 50B* (350 – 400 AD) and *58A* (290/300 – 375 AD) and with indistinct rim and flattened edge *Hayes 59B* (320 – 420 AD) can be traced back to fabric D1 (*pl. 8.5-7*). There are two decorated walls (*pl. 8.8-9*), pertaining to productions D1 and D2, which present stamped decorations of Style A(ii)-(iii), generically framed between the middle of the 4th and the middle of the 5th century.

4. Concluding remarks

The analysis of terra sigillata from the significant assemblage collected by Gr.A.V.O. offers insights into the socio-economic

landscape, illuminating the preferred supply routes for fine tableware over time.

Throughout the early imperial period, Italian wares, particularly Padana sigillata, fully met the high demand for fine pottery in rural settlements. These settlements began to develop concurrently with, or shortly after, the establishment of the *Iulia Concordia* colony in 42 or 40 BC. The findings corroborate the trend observed across *Venetia*³⁰: the vast majority of specimens (nearly 80% in this study) are attributable to local or regional manufacturers, with a significantly smaller proportion originating from central Italy. Padana sigillata fragments are ubiquitous across almost all sites examined, barring five contexts where their absence likely stems from gaps in documentation rather than an actual lack in the archaeological record³¹. Central Italian sigillata, while less abundant, is present at 12 sites, primarily interpreted as substantial *villae* and, in at least two instances, as modest farms³², suggesting a widespread, albeit quantitatively limited, presence in the region.

During this period, based on current evidence, imports from the provinces were scarce and did not appear to emerge before the latter half of the 1st century AD. The earliest imported piece appears to be a *Hayes 60* plate in ESB, not produced before the mid-1st century AD. Notably, this and other presumed ESB fragments were found exclusively at coastal sites in Brussa di Caorle, particularly at Are (site 154=26M). This location, strategically positioned near the mouth of the *Tiliaventum Maius*, was likely involved in commercial activities along the lagoon-maritime routes connecting the

upper Adriatic to the Mediterranean. While the limited quantity of materials precludes definitive conclusions, it's plausible that this coastal site functioned as a mediating emporium for these – and other – goods, likely destined for urban markets rather than widespread distribution across rural settlements³³.

Towards the end of the 1st century AD, trade flows brought prized moulded cups from southern Gaul into the region. On the contrary, plain Gaulish ware does not appear to have been widely distributed in *Iulia Concordia's* rural settlements. While this absence in the analyzed sample may partly result from artifact collection methodologies, the preference for moulded cups throughout the upper Adriatic is a well-documented trend³⁴. Gaulish sigillata from Ruthenian workshops shows a selective distribution pattern: specimens are found at only seven sites of considerable size and strategic topographic location³⁵, all situated in the eastern part of the territory, both along the final stretch of the *Tiliaventum* and north of the *Via Annia*, along the eastern road to *Noricum*. The large *villa rustica* at Borgo Valle (site 128=14M) is particularly noteworthy, yielding four of the ten South Gaulish fragments identified.

The mid-imperial period witnesses a significant decrease in attestations of fine tableware. With the cessation of Tardo Padana production, represented by a single example of a *Consp. 43* cup, only five cups demonstrate the distribution of 2nd-3rd century Padana products in the territory. Notably, no evidence of mid-Adriatic ware has been identified to date. Furthermore, the context

of these finds appears significant: they originate from five sites that had already distinguished themselves in the preceding phase by the quantity and quality of their sigillata fragments³⁶. Long-distance imports are limited to a Central Gaulish cup from Borgo Valle³⁷ and an African A2 plate from a small farm near the Livenza River, close to modern-day Biverone (site 77=02M).

Late antiquity is represented solely by a few ARSW fragments, found at just four sites along the final stretch of the *Tiliaventum Maius*, between Vado and its mouth (sites 66=09M, 127=15M, 128=14M, 157=26M), and at one site upstream of the *Via Annia*, interpreted as a large, long-lived *villa rustica* (site 55=34M). A possible LRC Ware fragment from Are might be associated with these, potentially confirming both the site's long occupation and ongoing contacts with the eastern Mediterranean, particularly the *Asia Minor* coast. The stark contrast between early imperial and later imperial fragments is evident: despite many settlements, especially in the coastal strip, seemingly continuing into the 4th-5th centuries, the scarcity of late sigillata suggests a significant economic contraction in extra-urban sites.

Within the broader Concordia territory, certain contexts stand out for both the quantity and variety of their assemblages, implying considerable social and economic significance. The sites interpreted as large *villae* at Roiatte Valladis (site 55=34M), Borgo Valle, and Are, along with the necropolis that developed at Vado along the *Via Annia* (66=09M), have yielded 58% of the analyzed fragments. These encompass Italian, African, Gaulish (Roiatte Valladis, Borgo Valle,

and Vado), and Eastern (Are) productions. The distribution of these settlements underscores the *Tiliaventum Maius*'s crucial role in fostering high-status sites, particularly at key junctures such as the road intersection between the Via Annia, the eastern road to *Noricum*, and the Tagliamento at Vado, and the river's lagoon entry point near Are, likely a stop on the lagoon route equipped with landing facilities.

Borgo Valle emerges as an exceptionally wealthy site. Its imports are particularly noteworthy, accounting for 15% of Central Italian sigillata and an impressive 45% of Gaulish examples, including the study's sole Central Gaulish fragment³⁸. Morphologically, the presence of mould-decorated cups (both Padana and Gaulish) and, more significantly, a rare vase-crater form, suggests

a taste for refined products. The substantial presence of mid-imperial Padana specimens (nearly 30%) further emphasizes this site's capacity to acquire fine wares even at an advanced stage, when other sites were already showing signs of economic decline.

These observations contribute to our understanding of the socio-economic landscape of Concordia's rural settlements and its evolution over time, aligning with patterns observed in other northern Italian territories bordering the Adriatic. While acknowledging the limitations of this sample - disconnected from stratigraphic context and often heterogeneous - the analysis of terra sigillata alone proves a valuable indicator of economic trends. Further examination of other pottery classes and, ideally, field verification, will only enhance these insights.

Acknowledgements

All images are reproduced with permission from the Italian Ministry of Culture. I would like to express my sincere gratitude to Philp Bes, Philip Kenrick, and Valentina Mantovani for their valuable suggestions, which significantly contributed to the improvement of this manuscript.

pl. 1. Plain North Italian terra sigillata.

pl. 2. Plain North Italian and Tardo Padana terra sigillata.

pl. 3. Mid-Imperial Padana terra sigillata.

pl. 4. Moulded North Italian terra sigillata.

pl. 5. Italian terra sigillata.

pl. 6. Italian terra sigillata.

pl. 7. Gaulish terra sigillata.

pl. 8. Eastern terra sigillata, Late Roman C Ware (?) and African Red Slip Ware.

Endnotes

¹ *Mappa* 1985; *Mappa* 2002.

² Regarding the outcomes of the research conducted to date on the villa and its surrounding territory, see the most recent works by CIGAINA *et al.* 2025 and BUSANA *et al.* 2025 in this volume.

³ BONOMI 1985; CIPRIANO-SANDRINI 2011; PRÖTTEL 1996, pp. 120-124; *Vasa Rubra* 2007.

⁴ BUORA 2005; CIPRIANO-SANDRINI 2003; DONAT 2015; *EAD* 2020; FASANO 1988, cc. 79-82; *Marina di Lugugnana* 1987, pp. 47-50; MASELLI SCOTTI 1974/1975.

⁵ The table has been compiled according to the information provided in *Mappa* 2002. The question marks adjacent to certain entries refer to information that is considered to require reassessment.

⁶ Among the examined sites, only the context at Are (site 157=26M) has undergone stratigraphic investigations, though these were not fully comprehensive. See BUSANA *et al.* 2025, with related bibliography.

⁷ Among these, only the site in Annone Veneto (54M) has yielded a considerable quantity of artifacts, suggesting the possibility of a *villa rustica*, although the extent of the scatter is unknown. The few finds from Fossalta di Portogruaro, Barbuio locality (site 33M), were accompanied by a handwritten note indicating “necropolis”. For the other contexts, the site typology is currently indeterminable.

⁸ For the purpose of treating the data uniformly, the site at Vado has also been included among the farms, as it was identified in the two maps elaborated by Gr.A.V.O. Regarding the possibility that it may instead be a necropolis area located along the Via Annia, see BUSANA *et al.* 2025, with related bibliography.

⁹ For the classification of forms, decorations, and maker’s stamps: *Conspectus* 1990; DRAGENDORFF 1895; HAYES 1972; *Id.* 1985; HOFMANN 1988; JORIO 2002; *Noricum* 2001; *OCK* 2000; OSWALD 1964; STUANI-MANTOVANI 2024.

¹⁰ The attribution of one of the three specimens to this type is questionable, as its rim appears rather flared.

¹¹ The stamp, for which an origin in Bologna is proposed given the high number of findings, is found exclusively on *Consp.* 38 cups. See CORTI 2015; *EAD* 2016.

¹² BUORA 2005; MANTOVANI-ARDIS 2021.

¹³ JORIO 2002, pp. 325-326; STUANI-MANTOVANI 2024, p. 419.

¹⁴ STUANI-MANTOVANI 2024, p. 419.

¹⁵ See most recently MANTOVANI 2015, pp. 72-74, form 5.

¹⁶ NEGRELLI 1998, p. 258, fig. 9, n. 58. The fragment under examination, however, exhibits distinct technical characteristics from those found in Faenza. Its ceramic fabric, orange in color (5YR 6/6 reddish yellow), is soft, slightly porous, and moderately refined, containing small white inclusions. The surface treatment consists of a thin, semi-transparent slip of matte red color (10R 4/6 red), which adheres poorly to the body and has largely flaked off. For comparison with the Faenza fragments, refer to NEGRELLI 1998, pp. 203-204.

¹⁷ MASELLI SCOTTI 1974/1975, pp. 494-495; *Vasa Rubra* 2007, pp. 254-255.

¹⁸ MANTOVANI 2015, pp. 90, 139, n.101.

¹⁹ MAZZEO SARACINO 1985, pp. 219-220.

²⁰ In the case of the specimen from Borgo Valle, the stamp is preserved in a fragmentary state and therefore cannot be identified with any of the numerous known variants. The stamp from Roiatte Valladis, although intact, is partially obscured by a circular impression; nevertheless, it allows for the reconstruction of the signature in the GELL variant (*OCK* 878.31-37).

²¹ The stamp identified in Teglio Veneto at Pars locality is comparable to the variant *OCK* 1408.12; whereas for the one from Borgo Valle, the fragmentary nature of the element does not allow for further type specification.

²² *Vasa Rubra* 2007, pp. 131-135, 174.

²³ The depiction of the bear is likely attributable to the punch Osw.1611 (OSWALD 1964, p. 107), while that of the vine scrolls corresponds to the punch H.329, catalogued based on the analysis of products from the Banassac workshop (HOFMANN 1988, p. 152). This latter punch has also been identified on another fragment of general South Gaulish production, found at Marina di Lugugnana, in a settlement near the Borgo Valle site.

²⁴ *NoTS* 3, pp. 129-130; GABUCCI 2017, p. 639, no. 27.

²⁵ MALFITANA 2005, pp. 134-137.

²⁶ I extend my sincere gratitude to Dr. Philip Bes, who has preliminarily proposed some interpretative hypotheses: the first, third, and fifth characters, in the Latin alphabet, can be identified with good probability as corresponding to the letters M, O, and L, while

it cannot be excluded that the other two symbols may not be alphabetic characters; the scholar also hypothesizes the possibility that the second grapheme might be a poorly impressed F. I also thank Dr. Philip Kenrick for his considerations regarding the use of the Latin alphabet, which would suggest the identification of a Western, possibly Italic, manufacture.

²⁷ The element under consideration exhibits a hard ceramic body of red color, moderately refined, with red and grey-brown inclusions. The slip, of a deep red color (10R 4/6 red), semi-matte, is thin, fairly adherent and covering, externally smoothed with a burnishing tool.

²⁸ GANDOLFI 2005b.

²⁹ HAYES 1972, pp. 329-338.

³⁰ MAGGI-MERLATTI 2015, p. 443; MANTOVANI-ARDIS 2020, p. 150.

³¹ These are, in fact, sites for which a very limited number of findings is available.

³² Among the sites that have yielded Italic terra sigillata is the context of Vado, previously interpreted as a farm but reinterpreted as a necropolis in light of new surface surveys. Located along the margins of the Via Annia, the burials would have had considerable visibility here, and it is therefore probable that they were reserved for prominent individuals who could afford a relatively high economic standard.

³³ The presence of Eastern sigillata, especially ESB, is well documented in *Concordia*, a center that was likely involved in the commercialization of these products towards the transalpine regions. See CIPRIANO-SANDRINI 2003, cols. 442-444.

³⁴ See most recently DONAT 2022, pp. 193-194.

³⁵ This specifically refers to 6 large *villae* and the necropolis along the *Via Annia* at Vado.

³⁶ The mid-imperial Padana fragments originate from the sites of Roiatte Valladis, Summaga, Borgo Valle, and Are, as well as from the farmstead at Palazzo Valle. The latter, however, yielded only two additional early imperial North Italian sigillata fragments.

³⁷ Noteworthy is the near-total absence of Central Gaulish imports, especially considering that the urban center of *Iulia Concordia* distinguishes itself from the rest of the upper Adriatic arc by the predominant presence of Central Gaulish wares over those from Southern Gaul (BONOMI 1984; CIPRIANO-SANDRINI 2011, p. 155; GABUCCI 2017, p. 585). The penetration of commercial flows from Central Gaul into the territory is evidenced by a single additional fragment found at Marina di Lugugnana (*Marina di Lugugnana* 1987, p. 50).

³⁸ The percentages proposed here and shortly thereafter should be considered indicative, owing to the quantitatively limited nature of the analyzed sample

References

- Atlante II = *Atlante delle forme cermiche. II. Ceramica fine romana nel bacino mediterraneo (Tardo Ellenismo e Primo Impero)*, Roma 1985.
- BONOMI 1985 = S. BONOMI, *Terra sigillata della Gallia da Iulia Concordia*, in "Archeologia Veneta", VII, 1985, pp. 213-243.
- BUORA 2005 = M. BUORA, *Nuovi marchi su terra sigillata dal territorio sud orientale dell'agro di Iulia Concordia*, in "Quaderni Friulani di Archeologia", XV, 2005, pp. 31-42.
- BUSANA et alii 2025 = M. S. BUSANA, F. PANDOLFO, A. VACILOTTO 2026, *Il progetto multidisciplinare "La villa romana di Mutteron dei Frati e il suo contesto". Primi risultati dall'indagine sul territorio*, in "Archeologia Veneta", XLVIII, 2025.
- CIGAINA et alii 2025 = L. CIGAINA, V. GOBBO, F. PANDOLFO, D. STEURNAGEL, A. VACILOTTO, *Bibione (Veneto), Mutteron dei Frati Excavations of the Roman villa, 2022-2024*, in "FOLD&R", Italy(604), 2025.
- CIPRIANO-SANDRINI 2003 = S. CIPRIANO, G. M. SANDRINI, *Sigillate orientali a Iulia Concordia. Primi dati da un'area campione. Lo scavo del piazzale antistante la cattedrale di Santo Stefano*, in "Aquileia Nostra", LXXIV, 2003, cc. 425-450.
- CIPRIANO-SANDRINI 2011 = S. CIPRIANO, G. M. SANDRINI, *La terra sigillata bollata da Iulia Concordia: sintesi dei dati*, in "Quaderni Friulani di Archeologia", XXI, 2011, pp. 153-164.
- CIVIDINI-MAGGI 2017 = T. CIVIDINI, P. MAGGI, *Ceramiche fini nel Medio Friuli: la distribuzione delle terre sigillate nelle campagne dell'agro aquileiese*, in G. LIPOVAC VRKLJAN, B. ŠILJEG, I. OŽANIC ROGLJIC, A. KONEŠTRA (eds.), *Rimske keramičarske i staklarske radionice. Proizvodnja i trgovina na jadranskom prostoru*, Zbornik III. međunarodnog arheološkog kolokvija (Crikvenica, 4-5.11.2014) / *Officine per la produzione di ceramica e vetro in epoca romana. Produzione e commercio nella regione adriatica*, Atti del III colloquio archeologico internazionale, Crikvenica 2017, pp. 207-223.
- Conspectus 1990 = E. ETTLINGER, B. HEDINGER, B. HOFFMANN, PH. KENRICK, G. PUCCI, K. ROTH-RUBI, G. SCHNEIDER, S. VON SCHNURBEIN, C.M. WELLS, S. ZABEHLICKY SCHEFFENEGER, *Conspectus formarum terrae sigillatae italico modo confectae*, Bonn 1990.
- CORTI 2015 = E. CORTI C., *Il bollo MAE/PATES su coppe Consp. 38 di produzione nord-italica*, in "Instrumentum", 42, 2015, pp. 17-19.
- CORTI 2016 = E. CORTI C., *Le coppe Haltern 14/Conspectus 38 in terra sigillata nord-italica. Produzione e diffusione*, in "RCRFA", 44, 2016, pp. 85-94.
- DONAT 2015 = P. DONAT, *Terra sigillata gallica in Italia nordorientale. Dalle collezioni museali alle scoperte recenti*, in "Quaderni Friulani di Archeologia", XXV, 2015, pp. 39-51.
- DONAT 2020 = P. DONAT, *Nuove testimonianze di terra sigillata gallica dal territorio di Iulia Concordia e di Oipertium nella collezione archeologica di Pasiano di Pordenone*, in "Quaderni Friulani di Archeologia", XXX, 2020, pp. 121-129.
- DONAT 2022 = P. DONAT, *Terre sigillate galliche. La collezione "storica" del Museo Archeologico Nazionale di Aquileia (Friuli Venezia Giulia - Italia)*, in G. LIPOVAC VRKLJAN, A. KONEŠTRA, A. ETEROVIĆ BORZIC (eds.), *Roman Pottery and Glass Manufactures: Production and Trade in the Adriatic Region and Beyond*, Proceedings of the 4th International Archaeological Colloquium (Crikvenica, 4-5 November 2017), (Archaeopress Roman Archaeology 94), Oxford 2022, pp. 191-202.
- DRAGENDORFF 1895 = H. DRAGENDORFF, *Terra Sigillata. Ein Beitrag zur Geschichte der griechischen und römischen Keramik*, in "Bonner Jahrbücher", 95, 1895 pp. 18-155.
- FASANO 1988 = M. FASANO, *Nuovi ritrovamenti di terra sigillata nord-italica decorata a matrice nel Friuli-Venezia Giulia*, in "Aquileia Nostra", LIX, 1988, cc. 77-104.
- GABUCCI 2017 = A. GABUCCI, *Attraverso le Alpi e lungo il Po. Importazione e distribuzione di sigillate galliche nella Cisalpina*, Rome 2018.
- GANDOLFI 2005a = D. GANDOLFI (a cura di), *La ceramica e i materiali di età romana. Classi, produzioni, commerci e consumi*, Bordighera (IM) 2005.

- GANDOLFI 2005b = D. GANDOLFI, *Sigillata focese («Late Roman C Ware»)*, in GANDOLFI 2005a, pp. 233-250.
- HAYES 1972 = J. W. HAYES, *Late Roman Pottery*, London 1972.
- HAYES 1985 = J. W. HAYES, *Sigillate orientali*, in *Atlante II*, pp. 1-96.
- HOFMANN 1988 = B. HOFMANN, *L'atelier de Banassac*, Gonfaron 1988.
- JORIO 2002 = S. JORIO, *Terra sigillata di media età imperiale di produzione padana. Contributo alla definizione di un repertorio lombardo*, in F. ROSSI (a cura di), *Nuove ricerche sul Capitolium di Brescia. Scavi, studi e restauri*, Milano 2002, pp. 323-352.
- MAGGI-MERLATTI 2015 = P. MAGGI, R. MERLATTI, *Ceramiche fini nell'alto Adriatico. Produzione e flussi commerciali tra II sec. a. C. e II sec. d. C.*, in Y. MARION, F. TASSAUX (eds.), *AdriAtlas et l'histoire de l'espace adriatique de VI^e s. a.C. au VIII^e s. p.C.*, Actes du colloque international de Rome (4-6 novembre 2013), (Scripta Antiqua 79), Bordeaux 2015, pp. 165-182.
- MALFITANA 2005 = D. MALFITANA, *Le terre sigillate ellenistiche e romane del Mediterraneo orientale. Aspetti, tipologie, produttivi ed economici*, in GANDOLFI 2005a, pp. 121-154.
- MANTOVANI 2015 = V. MANTOVANI, *Ceramiche fini da mensa di Adria romana. Le indagini di via Retratto (1982 e 1987)*, Roma 2015.
- MANTOVANI-ARDIS 2021 = V. MANTOVANI, C. ARDIS, *Le terre sigillate italiche con marchi di fabbrica: diffusione nel territorio friulano e confronto con alcuni siti campione di area veneta*, in P. VISENTINI, T. CIVIDINI, E. SCHINDLER KAUDELKA, P. VENTURA (a cura di), *L'archeologia di un territorio attraverso la ceramica: abitati, produzioni, scambi e commerci nel Friuli romano*, Atti della Giornata di Studio (Udine, 26 ottobre 2020), Udine 2021, pp. 147-200.
- Mappa 1985 = *Mappa Archeologica. Gli insediamenti d'epoca romana nell'agro Concordiese*, Torre di Mosto (VE) 1985.
- Mappa 2002 = *Ricerche di Topografia Archeologia nel Veneto Orientale. Mappa Archeologica aggiornata e informatizzata del Veneto Orientale*, Gruaro (VE) 2002.
- Marina di Lugugnana 1987 = *La villa romana di Marina di Lugugnana*, Pravisdomini (PN) 1987.
- MASELLI SCOTTI 1974/1975 = F. MASELLI SCOTTI, *Ceramica nord italica dell'agro di Iulia Concordia*, in "Aquileia Nostra", XLV-XLVI, 1974/1975, cc. 487-502.
- MAZZEO SARACINO 1985 = L. MAZZEO SARACINO, *Terra sigillata nord-italica*, in *Atlante II*, pp. 175-230.
- NEGRELLI 1998 = C. NEGRELLI, *Ceramica romana a Faenza. Terra sigillata nord-italica "tipo Sarius"* (prima parte), in "Faenza", LXXXIV, 1998, pp. 195-270.
- Noricum 2001 = E. SCHINDLER KAUDELKA, U. FASTNER, M. GRUBER, *Italische Terra Sigillata mit Appliken in Noricum*, Wien 2001.
- NoTS 3 = *Names on Terra Sigillata. An index of makers' stamps & signatures on Gallo-Roman Terra Sigillata (Samian Ware)*. Volume 3 (CERTIANUS to EXOBANO), London 2008.
- PRÖTTEL 1996 = Ph.M. PRÖTTEL, *Mediterrane Feinkeramikimporte des 2. bis 7. Jahrhunderts n. Chr. im oberen Adria-raum und Slowenien*, Espelkamp 1996.
- Ock 2000 = A. OXE, H. COMFORT, Ph. KENRICK, *Corpus Vasorum Arretinorum. A catalogue of the Signature, Shapes and Chronology of Italian Sigillata*, Bonn 2000.
- Oswald 1964 = F. OSWALD, *Index of Figures-Types on Terra Sigillata "Samian Ware"*, London 1964.
- Stuani-Mantovani 2024 = R. STUANI, V. MANTOVANI, *La terra sigillata padana di media età imperiale: status questionis e problemi aperti*, in "RCRFA", 48, 2024, pp. 441-426.
- Vasa Rubra 2007 = PETTENÒ E. (a cura di), *Vasa rubra. Marchi di fabbrica sulla terra sigillata da Iulia Concordia*, Padova 2007.

www.archeologicaveneta.com

*Finito di stampare
gennaio 2026*

*Grafiche TIOZZO
via Polonia, 9 - 35028 Piove di Sacco (PD)
info@grafichetiozzo.com
www.grafichetiozzo.com*